

stirred well with gradual addition of chloroacetyl chloride (0.005 mol, 6 ml) at 50–60° for 10–12 h and left at room temperature for 3 days. Excess of solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from 95% ethanol, (66%), m.p. 193° (Found: C, 63.76; H, 5.11; N, 6.76. $C_{23}H_{21}ClN_2O_2S$ requires: C, 63.99; H, 5.12; N, 6.78%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1680 (C=O), 700 (C–Cl), 1400 (C–N), 700 (C–S–C) and 3450 cm^{-1} (OH); m/z 363, 324 (base peak), 308, 248, 232, 206, 189, 177, 133, 105, 103, 91, 77, 68, 56 and 43.

Similarly other 2-azetidinone derivatives (2b–t) were prepared (Table 1).

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Synthesis and ^{13}C Nmr Study of 3-Aryloxymethyl-6-aryl-(7H)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new s-triazolothiadiazines as potential anthelmintic agents^{1,2}, we now report the synthesis of 3-aryloxymethyl-6-aryl-(7H)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (3) by the interaction of 3-aryloxymethyl 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles¹ (1) with α -bromo-substituted-acetophenones (2)

A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), 2 (0.01 mol) and pyridine (1.2 cm^3) was refluxed in absolute alcohol (50 cm^3) for 4 h. Alcohol was then distilled off and the residue treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid, washed with water and filtered. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

The ir spectra (KBr) of 1 displayed bands due to 1,2,4-triazoles at 3230, 2720, 1635, 1570 and 1470 cm^{-1} . In addition, strong intensity band at 1250–1200 cm^{-1} and medium intensity band at 1070–1000 cm^{-1} due to aromatic ether

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	65	132	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃
b	H	CH ₃	71	186	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃
c	H	Cl	75	154	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃
d	CH ₃	H	68	220	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃
e	CH ₃	CH ₃	64	202	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃
f	CH ₃	Cl	72	172	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃
g	Cl	H	74	168	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃
h	Cl	CH ₃	70	183	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₃
i	Cl	Cl	75	166	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₃

linkage^{3,4} were obtained. The absence of carbonyl frequency at 1725–1705 cm^{-1} , (further confirmed by ^{13}C nmr spectra) and SH stretching vibrations at 2600–2550 cm^{-1} confirmed the cyclic structure 3.

The ^{13}C nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of 3d showed signals due to 18-carbon atoms in the molecule. The signals due to carbons (C=N) at C-3, C-4 and C-6 positions were observed at 141.6, 150.4 and 154.0 ppm respectively. The methylenic carbon C-2, methyl carbon C-1 and the (7H) carbon C-5 showed signals at 59.6, 23.6 and 24.9 ppm respectively. The 3-aryloxy aromatic carbons showed signals at 158.3, 115.5, 129.1 and 133.5 ppm due to C-1'; C-2',6'; C-3',5' and C-4' respectively. The 6-aryl aromatic carbons showed signals at 115.1, 127.4, 129.6 and 121.8 ppm due to C-1''; C-2'',6''; C-3'',5'' and C-4'' respectively.

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Chemical Examination of Pods of *Cassia roxburghii*

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EARLIER, we communicated the isolation and structural elucidation of roxburghinol¹, a new 1,2-dihydroanthraquinone and roxburghin², a new tetrahydroxystilbene from the leaves and wood of the *Cassia roxburghii* Benth. respectively. In the present communication, the results of chemical examination of pods of this plant is reported.

The air-dried and powdered pods of *C. roxburghii* were extracted with methanol. The solvent-free residue was separated into petroleum ether solubles and insolubles. The petroleum ether solubles on column chromatographic separation (silica gel) led to the isolation of two compounds, designated as compounds A and B.

Compound-A (0.002%), m.p. 138°, $[\alpha]_D -36^\circ$, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$, M^+ 414, gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt test³ for sterols and was characterised as β -sitosterol⁴ by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound-B, crystallised from chloroform as orange flakes (0.0015%), m.p. 196°, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$, M^+ 254, gave pink colour with alcoholic magnesium acetate indicating it to be a hydroxy-anthraquinone⁵. From the spectral data (ir, uv, ^1H nmr, mass) and also by a direct comparison, it was identified as 1,8-dihydroxy-3-methylantraquinone (chrysophanol)².

The petroleum ether insoluble fraction, after the usual work up, followed by column chromatography (silica gel), yielded three compounds, designated as compounds C, D and E. Compound-C crystallised from CHCl_3 -acetone (9; 1, v/v) as cream coloured fluffly solid (0.002%), m.p. 224°,

$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$, M^+ 214, formed tetraacetate and tetramethyl ether. From the analytical and spectral data (ir, uv, ^1H nmr, ^{13}C nmr and mass) it was identified as roxburghin³, which was confirmed by a direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound-D crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.003%), m.p. 140–42°, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$, M^+ 194, did not give any colour tests, and was characterised as terephthalic acid⁶ by its spectral data and also by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

- 1; R=R'=H
2; R=R'=Ac
3; R=CH₃, R'=H

Compound-E (1) crystallised from chloroform as light cream coloured flakes (0.01%), m.p. 242°, $[\alpha]_D -56.66^\circ$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$, M^+ 274, gave characteristic colour reactions of flavan-3-ols⁷. It formed a tetraacetate (2), m.p. 127°, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_9$, M^+ 442 and a trimethyl ether (3), m.p. 110°, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$, M^+ 316, indicating the presence of three phenolic hydroxyls and one alcoholic hydroxyl group. The ir spectrum (KBr) of 1 showed characteristic bands at 3300–3500 cm⁻¹ (OH), 2900 (aliphatic CH), 1500–1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C). Its uv spectrum, λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 228sh (4.71) and 270 nm (4.12) was similar to those of flavan-3-ols⁸. The overall signal pattern of compound-E in its ^1H nmr spectrum (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) bears resemblances to that of flavan-3-ols⁹, δ 2.88 (2H, m, H-4a, H-4b), 3.2 (1H, m, D₂O exchangeable, C₃-OH), 4.2 (1H, m, H-3), 4.87 (1H, d, J 1.7 Hz, H-2), 5.96 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.05 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.75 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 7.27 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 8.46 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable, C₅-OH), 8.57 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable, C₇-OH) and 8.79 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable, C_{4'}-OH). Hence compound-E was characterised as 4',5,7-trihydroxyflavan-3-ol. The mass spectrum of 1 showed prominent ions at m/z 274 [M]⁺ (100), 256 [$M-\text{H}_2\text{O}$] (10), 136 (RDA fragment) (40) and 139 (RDA fragment with proton shift) (97) supporting the assigned structure¹⁰. The compound showed negative Cotton effect in its CD spectrum. The sign and magnitude is almost identical to that of (-) epiafzelechin¹¹. Thus compound-E was characterised as (-) epiafzelechin, which was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The ^{13}C nmr spectrum (39.2 MHz, DMSO-d₆) of 1 showed the appropriate signals for 12 chemically different carbon atoms. The peak positions